

MEDICAL SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RATE OF NEURONAL DEGENERATION OF THE BRAIN IN PATIENTS WITH SYMPTOMATIC EPILEPSY AND CEREBROVASCULAR DISORDERS OF VARIOUS ETIOLOGIES

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Abstract

Epilepsy is a common chronic disease of the brain. The incidence of epilepsy increases significantly with age, particularly after the age of 55. It may act both as a cause of progressive neuronal loss in the brain and as a consequence of this irreversible process. In the present study, the risks of developing dementia in patients with epilepsy as well as in those with non-epileptic cerebrovascular diseases of the brain were analyzed.

Objective:

To investigate, in a comparative aspect, the probability of the influence of symptomatic forms of epilepsy and various cerebrovascular pathologies of the brain without epilepsy on the intensity of neurodegeneration development.

Materials and Methods:

A direct prospective study conducted over a three-year period (2022–2025) using the Arizona questionnaire, the 6CIT, and the MMSE tests included 406 patients aged 50 years and older. The study revealed the presence of a pronounced neurodegenerative process in patients with epilepsy, especially in cases combined with cerebrovascular pathology.

Considerations:

An important observation was the absence of severe dementia during one year of follow-up, which may indicate the presence of a potential “therapeutic window.”

Discussion:

The final results of the study demonstrated the necessity of developing targeted recommendations for patients with comorbid pathology that take into account the combined impact of epilepsy and cerebrovascular diseases of the brain.

Keywords: epilepsy, neurodegeneration, dementia, cerebrovascular diseases of the brain.

Introduction. Epilepsy is a common chronic disease of the brain. This neurological disorder, known since ancient times, is characterized by recurrent unprovoked epileptic seizures [1,2]. The incidence of the disease increases most notably in old age, especially after the age of 55 [2,7]. Numerous studies demonstrate the development of cognitive impairment in patients with seizures that persist for decades [3,4,6]. Importantly, there is a complex relationship between epilepsy and neurodegeneration. Epilepsy may be both the cause of progressive neuronal loss in the brain and a consequence of this irreversible process [3,5].

According to numerous scientific studies, diseases of the central nervous system of various etiologies may lead to dementia [8,9]. Despite the high and meaningful probability of neurodegenerative processes – dementia – in patients with long-term epilepsy, vascular pathologies of the brain, or both, the degree of influence of these comorbidities on the survival of brain nerve cells has not been sufficiently studied [2,5,10]. Therefore, specific clinical recommendations for reducing the risk of dementia in these conditions are still lacking. In this study, we analyzed the risk of developing dementia in patients with epilepsy as well as in patients with other non-epileptic cerebrovascular brain diseases.

Objective. To study the likelihood of the influence of symptomatic forms of epilepsy and various cerebrovascular brain pathologies without epilepsy on the intensity of neurodegeneration, in a comparative manner.

Material and Methods. The study was conducted at the Republican Psychiatric Hospital No. 1 located in the Mashtaga settlement of Baku and at the Department of Neurology and Clinical Neurophysiology of the Azerbaijan State Institute for Advanced Medical Training named after A. Aliev. Patients were selected from the 1st and 2nd geriatric departments of the hospital. Age, sex, neurological symptoms, onset, and causes of the disease were determined.

Neurophysiological (EEG) and neuroimaging (CT, MRI) methods were used. To determine the level of cognitive disorders in dynamics, the Arizona Questionnaire, 6CIT, and MMSE tests were applied. The diagnosis and seizure semiology in patients with epilepsy were determined in accordance with the 2017 International League Against Epilepsy (ILAE) classification. Diagnoses in patients with

non-epileptic CNS disorders were established according to the ICD-10.

Statistical processing of the obtained data was performed using Statistica 8.0 for Windows (StatSoft Inc., USA).

Results. A direct prospective study was conducted for 5 years, from 2021 to 2025, covering 406 patients aged 50 and older. The age range of all patients was 50–86 years. Among them, 125 (30.8%) patients had epilepsy, 254 (62.6%) had various cerebrovascular brain diseases without epilepsy, and the control group included 27 (6.7%) patients aged 70+ (72–86 years) without gross pathological cerebrovascular manifestations on neuroimaging (MRI, CT) and without epilepsy. MRI

and CT scans of these patients revealed age-related atrophic changes, empty sella, and isolated microangiopathic foci in the hemispheres. Patients with epilepsy had symptomatic forms. They were divided into 2 subgroups: subgroup 1 – epilepsy of cerebrovascular origin (23 cases, 18.4%); subgroup 2 – symptomatic epilepsy of other origins (102 cases, 81.6%) including frontal (37 cases, 29.6%), temporal (49 cases, 39.2%), occipital (8 cases, 6.4%), parietal (4 cases, 3.2%), and mesial temporal sclerosis (MTS) (4 cases, 3.2%). Patients were enrolled continuously during the study period and assigned to corresponding groups.

Table 1.

Distribution of patients by sex

Groups	Patients	Total number	Sex	
			male	female
I	Patients with Epilepsy	125 (30,8%)	72 (57,6%)	53 (42,4)
	Epilepsy of cerebrovascular origin	23 (18,4%)	10 (43,4%)	13 (56,5%)
	Other forms of symptomatic epilepsy:	102 (81,6%)	62 (60,8%)	40 (39,2%)
	Frontal focal epilepsy	37 (29,6%)	19 (51,4%)	18 (48,6%)
	Temporal mixed epilepsy	49 (39,2%)	35 (71,4%)	14 (28,6%)
	focal epilepsy	8 (6,4%)	3 (37,5%)	5 (62,5%)
	Parietal focal epilepsy	4 (3,2%)	3 (75%)	1 (25%)
	MTS (mesial temporal sclerosis)	4 (3,2%)	2 (50%)	2 (50%)
II	Patients with Cerebrovascular Pathology (CVP) without Epilepsy	254 (62,6%)	139 (54,7%)	115 (45,2%)
	Arterial hypertension	6 (2,3%)	3 (50%)	3 (50%)
	Ischemic brain disease	186 (73,2%)	98 (52,7%)	88 (47,3%)
	Vascular phakomatoses	2 (0,8%)	2 (100%)	-
	Ischemic stroke	12 (4,7%)	7 (58,3%)	5 (1,96%)
	Microangiopathic foci on MRI	48 (18,9%)	29 (60,4%)	19 (39,6%)
III Control group	Healthy elderly controls	27 (6,7%)	10 (37,0%)	17 (62,9%)
Total:		406 (100%)	221 (54,4%)	185 (45,6%)

Patients with cerebrovascular pathologies suffered from grade II arterial hypertension in 6 (2.3%) individuals, ischemic heart disease in 186 (73.2%) individuals, vascular phakomatoses in 2 (0.8%) individuals, ischemic stroke in 12 (4.7%) individuals, and multiple nonspecific microangiopathic, gliotic, and atherosclerotic brain lesions in 48 (18.9%) individuals. All patients were under routine medical supervision in accordance with the regulations of the respective medical

services in the hospital departments. The conditions of medical care and nursing for patients in the study group did not differ from those provided to patients in the non-study group.

At the beginning of the study, as shown in Table 2, patients' relatives were assessed for the current level of cognitive impairment in the examined individuals using the Arizona questionnaire.

Table 2.

Results of the Arizona Cognitive Test across all three study groups				
Groups	Patients tested (relatives interviewed)	Results: (0–4: Normal; 5–14: Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI); >14: Dementia)		
		Results (range)	female	male
I	Patients with Epilepsy	5-14	7-14	5-13
	Epilepsy of cerebrovascular origin	9-14	9-14	9-13
	Other forms of symptomatic epilepsy:	5-14	7-14	5-12
	Frontal focal epilepsy	7-12	8-11	5-12
	Temporal mixed epilepsy	8-14	10-14	8-12
	focal epilepsy	5-7	7	5-7
	Parietal focal epilepsy	9-14	10-14	9-12
	MTS (mesial temporal sclerosis)	10-12	11-12	10-11
II	Patients with Cerebrovascular Pathology (CVP) without Epilepsy	5-12	7-12	5-10
	Arterial hypertension	10-11	10	11
	Ischemic brain disease	5-9	7-9	5-8
	Vascular phakomatoses	12, 13	12, 13	-
	Ischemic stroke	7-13	8-12	7-13
	Microangiopathic foci on MRI	6-12	6-9	8-12
III-Control group	Healthy elderly controls	5-7	6	5-7
For all patients:		5-14	7-14	5-13

The level of development of the neurodegenerative process at the time of study initiation, as presented

in Table 3, was assessed in each patient using the 6CIT test.

Table 3.

Cognitive deficit level according to the 6CIT scale				
Groups	Patients:	Results: (0–7: Normal; 8–9: Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI); 10–28: Moderate/Severe Cognitive Impairment)		
		Results (range)	female	male
I	Patients with Epilepsy	8-10	9-10	8-9
	Epilepsy of cerebrovascular origin	8-10	10	9
	Other forms of symptomatic epilepsy:	8-10	9-10	10
	Frontal focal epilepsy	8-9	9	8
	Temporal mixed epilepsy	8-10	10	9
	focal epilepsy	8	9	8
	Parietal focal epilepsy	10	10	10
	MTS (mesial temporal sclerosis)	10	10	10
II	Patients with Cerebrovascular Pathology (CVP) without Epilepsy	9-10	9-10	9-10
	Arterial hypertension	10	10	9
	Ischemic brain disease	9	9	10
	Vascular phakomatoses	10	10	-
	Ischemic stroke	9	9	9
	Microangiopathic foci on MRI	10	10	10
III-control group	Healthy elderly controls	9-10	9	10
All patients:		8-10	9-10	8-10

Subsequently, every 4 months—that is, three times over the course of one year (at the 4th, 8th, and 12th months)—the patients underwent testing using the

MMSE, as shown in the three consecutively presented Tables 4, 5, and 6. In order to increase the sensitivity of the test, the final item involving a drawing was replaced

with the Clock Drawing Test, which independently demonstrates high reliability and specificity.

Table 4.

Cognitive deficit level according to MMSE (first test, after 4 months)				
Groups	Patients:	Results: (28–30: Normal; 24–27: Pre-dementia cognitive impairment; 20–23: Mild dementia; 11–19: Moderate dementia; 0–10: Severe dementia)		
		Results (range)	female	male
I	Patients with Epilepsy	21-23	21-22	22-23
	Epilepsy of cerebrovascular origin	22-23	22	23
	Other forms of symptomatic epilepsy:	21-23	21-22	23
	Frontal focal epilepsy	22-23	22	23
	Temporal mixed epilepsy	21-23	21	22
	focal epilepsy	22-23	22	23
	Parietal focal epilepsy	21-22	21	22
	MTS (mesial temporal sclerosis)	22	22	22
II	Patients with Cerebrovascular Pathology (CVP) without Epilepsy	22-23	22	23
	Arterial hypertension	23	22	23
	Ischemic brain disease	22	22	22
	Vascular phakomatoses	22	22	-
	Ischemic stroke	22	22	22
	Microangiopathic foci on MRI	22	22	22
III-control group	Healthy elderly controls	22-23	22	23
All patients:		21-23	21-22	21-22

Table 5.

Cognitive deficit level according to MMSE (second test, after 8 months)				
Groups	Patients:	Results: (28–30: Normal; 24–27: Pre-dementia cognitive impairment; 20–23: Mild dementia; 11–19: Moderate dementia; 0–10: Severe dementia)		
		Results (range)	female	male
I	Patients with Epilepsy	18-20	18-20	18-20
	Epilepsy of cerebrovascular origin	20	20	20
	Other forms of symptomatic epilepsy:	18-20	19-20	18-20
	Frontal focal epilepsy	20	20	20
	Temporal mixed epilepsy	19	19	19
	focal epilepsy	20	20	20
	Parietal focal epilepsy	18	19	18
	MTS (mesial temporal sclerosis)	19	19	19
II	Patients with Cerebrovascular Pathology (CVP) without Epilepsy	18-20	18-20	18-20
	Arterial hypertension	20	20	20
	Ischemic brain disease	20	20	20
	Vascular phakomatoses	19	19	-
	Ischemic stroke	19	19	19
	Microangiopathic foci on MRI	18	18	18
III-control group	Healthy elderly controls	20	20	20
All patients:		18-20	18-20	18-20

Table 6.

Cognitive deficit level according to MMSE (third test, after 12 months)

Groups	Patients:	Results: (28–30: Normal; 24–27: Pre-dementia cognitive impairment; 20–23: Mild dementia; 11–19: Moderate dementia; 0–10: Severe dementia)		
		Results (range)	female	male
I	Patients with Epilepsy	15-17	15-17	16-17
	Epilepsy of cerebrovascular origin	16	15	17
	Other forms of symptomatic epilepsy:	15-17	15-17	16-17
	Frontal focal epilepsy	17	17	17
	Temporal mixed epilepsy	16	16	16
	focal epilepsy	17	20	20
	Parietal focal epilepsy	15	15	16
	MTS (mesial temporal sclerosis)	17	17	17
II	Patients with Cerebrovascular Pathology (CVP) without Epilepsy	15-17	15-17	16-17
	Arterial hypertension	17	17	17
	Ischemic brain disease	17	17	17
	Vascular phakomatoses	16-17	16, 17	-
	Ischemic stroke	15-16	15	16
	Microangiopathic foci on MRI	15-16	15	16
III-control group	Healthy elderly controls	20	20	20
All patients:		15-20	15-20	15-20

Based on the conducted study, it was found that female patients predominated over male patients in the first and second groups. In the third group, however, men outnumbered women by seven individuals. The level of cognitive functioning in patients from all groups, assessed using the Arizona questionnaire, ranged from 5 to 14 points. This indicates that the observed patients already had moderate cognitive impairment. A comparative analysis using this questionnaire within each group and between the groups revealed certain differences. Thus, the most pronounced cognitive impairment among patients with epilepsy was observed in those whose seizures were provoked by cerebrovascular pathology of the brain. In patients with epilepsy of non-cerebrovascular origin, cognitive decline was more evident in individuals with temporal and parietal seizures. Among patients in the second study group, those who had suffered a stroke and those with vascular phakomatoses demonstrated comparatively greater impairment of cognitive functioning. Patients from the third study group were characterized by a relatively mild level of moderate cognitive deficit.

Subsequently, during direct testing of the patients themselves using the 6CIT questionnaire, both moderate and severe cognitive impairments were identified. A comparison of the results obtained from the two tests (the Arizona questionnaire and the 6CIT) helped confirm the presence of cognitive dysfunction in all patients participating in the study; moreover, when patients were tested directly, the degree of cognitive deficit appeared to be slightly higher [11]. Four months after the 6CIT assessment, all patients were evaluated for changes in cognitive impairment dynamics using the MMSE test [12]. According to the results of the MMSE, which was administered three times at four-

month intervals, noticeable declines in cognitive functioning occurred during the second and third assessments, that is, after 8 and 12 months from the start of the study. No cases of severe dementia were detected in any patient during the one-year follow-up period.

The neuronal cells of patients in the third study group proved to be remarkably resilient. The poorest outcomes were observed in patients from the first group with epilepsy of cerebrovascular origin, as well as with temporal and parietal forms of epilepsy. In the second group, the most cognitively affected patients were those with phakomatoses, those who had experienced a stroke, and those with multiple microangiopathic lesions in the brain. Our attention was also drawn to the highest levels of cognitive deficit observed in patients with the parietal form of epilepsy and epilepsy of cerebrovascular origin, as well as in individuals with multiple microangiopathic lesions in the cerebral hemispheres, in comparative analysis.

Statistical analysis performed using the Statistica 8.0 software determined the level of reliability of the obtained results. Pearson's χ^2 test and the nonparametric Friedman test were used to assess differences between groups. According to the Arizona questionnaire, differences between the groups were not statistically significant, since all patients had cognitive impairment; the differences were observed only in the degree of its severity.

Based on the analysis of changes in cognitive function levels in the examined patients according to the MMSE scale, conducted at four-month intervals over one year, a statistically significant decline in cognitive status was identified in patients with epilepsy and cerebrovascular diseases. Differences between the groups were statistically significant (Friedman test, χ^2

= 248.5, $p < 0.005$). A graphical representation is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Dynamics of cognitive decline (MMSE) across groups

A separate analysis of epilepsy forms demonstrated the greatest decline in cognitive status in patients with parietal and temporal epilepsy, as well as in those with epilepsy of vascular origin. Patients with the occipital form of epilepsy showed the least decline in cognitive functions (MMSE = 20), whereas parietal and temporal localizations were associated with the most

pronounced impairments (MMSE = 15 and 16, respectively). The mean scores in patients with MTS and epilepsy of cerebrovascular origin were 17 and 16, respectively. Statistical analysis revealed significant differences between the subgroups ($p < 0.005$, Kruskal–Wallis test). A graphical representation is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. MMSE decline by epilepsy subtypes

In the group of patients with epilepsy of vascular origin, the mean MMSE score decreased from 22 to 16 over 12 months. In patients with cerebrovascular disorders without epilepsy, the average decline was 6 points (from 22.5 to 16.5). Meanwhile, in the control group, no statistically significant decline in cognitive function was observed (average 22.5 → 20). Sex had no statistically significant effect on the dynamics of cognitive impairment.

Discussion:

The obtained data confirm the presence of a pronounced neurodegenerative process in patients with epilepsy, especially when cerebrovascular pathology is present [1, 2]. The significant decline in cognitive status over one year, as recorded by the MMSE and other scales, may indicate more rapid progression of neurodegeneration when seizure syndrome and vascular disorders coexist [3–5]. According to the literature, adult

epilepsy is highly likely associated with an increased risk of future dementia. This is supported by the conclusions of at least a dozen studies reporting post-epileptic dementia risk ratios often above 2 and sometimes higher [10].

In our study, parietal and temporal localization of foci, as well as the presence of mesial temporal sclerosis (MTS), were associated with the worst cognitive outcomes [4, 6, 13]. The presence of cardiovascular/cerebrovascular factors (stroke, hypertension, ischemic heart disease, diabetes, dyslipidemia) further increases this risk—the combination of epilepsy and vascular pathology confers a higher probability of dementia than either condition alone [14]. Moreover, the onset of epilepsy at a later age often signals underlying cerebrovascular disease or neurodegeneration, serving as an important clinical marker of elevated risk for cognitive decline [15].

The control group demonstrated relative stability, supporting its representativeness for age-related norms [1, 7]. Another important observation was the absence of severe dementia during the one-year follow-up, suggesting the presence of a potential “therapeutic window” [8]. These results emphasize the need to develop targeted recommendations for patients with comorbid conditions, including epilepsy and cerebrovascular disease [2, 9, 10].

Conclusion:

The results of this prospective observation indicate a significant difference in the rate of cognitive decline among patients with various forms of symptomatic epilepsy and cerebrovascular disorders [3, 5]. Temporal, parietal, and cerebrovascular forms of epilepsy have the greatest impact on cognitive deterioration [4, 6].

These findings highlight the need for earlier and more targeted interventions in the management of these patient groups, given the high likelihood of neurodegenerative outcomes [2, 8]. At the same time, the stability of cognitive status in the control group confirms the influence of the studied nosologies on the pace of neurodegeneration [1, 7].

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